

LISTEN-E

DeveLoping new awareness and Innovative toolS to support efficient waTer rEsources management
Exploiting geoinformatiOn technologies

D5.2 – Project Website

Contributing Work Package	Work Package 5: “Products Dissemination & Public Engagement”
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document constitutes the deliverable D.5.1 Project website, which is part of Work Package 5, which has to be delivered during the first month (M1), and this represents the description of the deliverable product of the website. The project website was developed at the beginning of the project, and its main purpose is to maintain communication between the progress and the results of the project and the public, which is part of the plan to disseminate and exploit the results of the project until its completion.

The LISTEN-EO website will represent the main way of communication within the project including all the necessary information about the project, public materials, public deliverables, dissemination materials, news, events, newsletter, and other information specific to the project.

The website was publicly launched on social networks starting with the first month (M1) of the project and will be updated with new information monthly.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope

The website is part of the plan for disseminating information and the results of the project, thus making it the most important way of communication and dissemination of information to the public space. It was launched in the first month (M1) of the project and the research team will be responsible for the maintenance and updating of the website throughout the duration of the project.

1.2. Document Structure

- Section 1 - An outline of the deliverable's purpose and extent.
- Section 2 - An inventory and explanation of the goals within the LISTEN-EO website for the project.
- Section 3 - A depiction of the requirements that served as the foundation for designing and developing the website.
- Section 4 - A description of the pages, sections, and features within the LISTEN-EO website.

2. Website objectives

The primary aim of the LISTEN-EO project website is to effectively communicate and share information regarding the project's status, advancements, and, notably, its outcomes. This website serves as the principal communication platform for the project, providing the latest information on the project's progress and significant achievements to the intended audience.

LISTEN-EO website offers a user-friendly interface with a straightforward navigation structure, ensuring that users can effortlessly access all the content. The inclusion of graphic illustrations in the content aids in a quicker and more accessible understanding of project details. The platform is designed for easy updates, making it convenient to update and add new content, whether it's related to news, publications, or other essential data. To enhance user engagement, the website is equipped with social media integration, allowing users to seamlessly connect with the project's social networks. The website will maintain by the fellow during the whole period of the project.

Figure 1. LISTEN-EO website: <https://listeneo.wixsite.com/listen-eo>

3. Website requirements

These specifications guided the development process to create a website that effectively serves its intended goals. The requirements for the LISTEN-EO website encompassed functionality, structure,

features, and alignment with the website's overarching mission, ensuring it remains consistent with its ultimate purpose.

3.1. Technical Requirements

The LISTEN-EO website was created with close attention to specific technical needs. We used the user-friendly WIX platform, secured the domain www.listen-eo.gr, which offers also capabilities of our website visitors tracking and is also paired with Google Analytics, one of the most popular website visitor tracking tools globally, providing relevant statistics on demand. Additionally, we included features like social media links and a newsletter to enhance user engagement and visibility. For the technical requirements of the website, we focused on ensuring that its functionality, structure, and features to align with its overarching mission and purpose. These specifications guided the development process to create a website that effectively serves its intended goals. For the design and development process of the website the WIX platform was used due to its user-friendly interface and built-in accessibility features. The website hosting will be at the WIX platform.

3.2. Technical Requirements

The development of the WIX platform website designer also gave paramount importance to user requirements. To enhance accessibility, Clear and consistent navigation options were integrated to facilitate seamless user journeys, and form elements included well-associated labels to improve usability and accessibility.

4. Technical Requirements

4.1. Project's identity

The visual identity represents an important way of promoting the project and disseminating information about it. LISTEN-EO presents a visual identity consisting of its own logo. In the construction of the website, visual identity was implemented, representing the display of the logo whenever possible, as well as the application of the range of own colors for the coloring of the website and graphic materials. Thus, a blue-white palette was adopted, which gives uniformity and its own identity to the project, both at the level of images, illustrations, buttons, and at the level of the coloring of the sections or the text.

5. Technical Requirements

5.1. Project's identity

The users' personal data on the LISTEN-EO website, is handled with great care. The Privacy Policy provides a transparent and easily understandable overview of the website's data management practices, giving you the knowledge to make informed decisions regarding the sharing of your personal information, including when and how to do so.

6. Website Structure

The main menu of the project web page is structured in a way that allows 6 key selection features which are shown below

Home About ResearchTeam Objectives Communication & Dissemination Contact

Figure 2: Website header

In the next sub-sections are shown the selections under each of those features.

6.1. Home

The LISTEN-EO website's homepage functions as the central hub of the project, providing a thorough overview of the website's features. At the top of the page, a banner showcases the project's theme, complemented by a brief description within a transparent rectangle just above it which contains the title and logo acknowledgment. The banner provides a direct link between the homepage feature selection from the banner and the respective section is provided.

The website page concludes by displaying navigation options and contact information at the page footer, which remains accessible across every other page.

Home About ResearchTeam Objectives Communication & Dissemination Contact

Welcome to LISTEN-EO

DeveLoping new awareness and Innovative toolS to support
efficient waTer rEsources maNagement Exploiting geoinformatiOn
technologies

Figure 3: Website Home page header

Similarly, the website footer is shown in the figure below.

Figure 4: Website footer

6.2. About us

The "About Us" section serves as the narrative core of the LISTEN-EO project, encompassing a briefly description and characterization of the project while effectively conveying its overarching purpose. This section succinctly outlines the project's primary mission.

Figure 5. "About" section

6.3. Research Team

The "Research Team" section offers a brief presentation of the research team members involved in the LISTEN-EO project.

Research Team

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Figure 6. "Research Team" section

6.4. Objectives

The "Objectives" section offers a brief description of the project's main goals and provides detailed information about the individual work packages.

LISTEN-EO OBJECTIVES

Perform a series of cutting-edge inventions to the SimSphere LBM through a multifaceted approach, expanding the functionalities and usability of this land surface modeling tool.

Refine the 'triangle' inversion modeling approach to gain a deeper understanding of physical properties within the EO-derived Ts/VI feature space.

Establish the downscaling of existing soil moisture EO products, improving the usability of those products for watershed to regional studies.

Figure 7. "Objectives" section

Work Packages

Figure 8. WPs structure and interconnectivity figure located under “Objectives” section

6.5. About us

The communication and dissemination functionality serves the purpose of providing the public with comprehensive information and publicly accessible materials delivered by the project. This is achieved by presenting publications and deliverables in a tabular format with two rows, which pop up on a subpage when the user clicks on them.

Figure 9. “Communication & Dissemination” section

Publications

Articles to international journals

Presentations

Deliverables

D1.1 | Ethics and Quality Management Plan

D1.2 | Data Management Plan

Figure 10. The sub-sections of “Publications” & “Deliverables” located under the “Communication & Dissemination” section

6.6. Contact

The contact section, located at the main homepage, serves to provide users with contact a contact form that can be used to send suggestions or questions to the project team. On the right-hand side of the section, it offers specific project email details and individual contact information.

Connect with us!

Project Coordinator:
 Dept. of Geography, Harokopio
 University of Athens, Greece

Principal Investigator:
 Dr. George P. Petropoulos
 listen_eo@hua.gr
 (gpetropoulos@hua.gr)

First Name

Last Name

Email *

Message

Thanks for submitting!

Figure 10. Contact section

6.7. Newsletter Signup

The Newsletter Signup banner is located at the bottom of the website page. The users have the option to subscribe to the newsletter, allowing the project to create an email database for efficiently delivering updates to readers in electronic format.

Subscribe to Our Newsletter

Enter your email here *

Sign Up

Thanks for submitting!

Figure 11. Newsletter Signup

7. About us

The scope of the present report has been to present a summary of the LISTEN-EO project web page's main functionalities, which consists one of the project deliverables. The web page content is going to be dynamically updated with information added in it at least once a month, as the project evolves. The domain name will be maintained throughout the project duration, and it will also be maintained for another 5 years after the end of the project as required by the funding body (ref: ΟΔΗΓΟΣ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗΣ ΚΑΙ ΥΛΟΠΟΙΗΣΗΣ ΕΡΓΩΝ ΕΛΙΔΕΚ).